

FUNCTIONAL MODELLING OF DAMAGES RESULTING FROM ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS INVOLVING UNREGISTERED VEHICLES

Zoran Joševski

Faculty of Technical Sciences– Bitola
zoran.josevski@uklo.edu.mk

Verče Koneska

Faculty of Technical Sciences – Bitola
verce.koneska@uklo.edu.mk

Stevcho Jolakoski

Faculty of Security – Skopje
stevco.jolakoski@uklo.edu.mk

Goran Angelovski

President of the Republic Council for Traffic Safety of the Republic of North Macedonia,
goranangelovski@rsbsp.org.mk

Abstract

This paper develops conceptual and analytical functional models for the quantitative assessment of road traffic risk through a comprehensive analysis of data related to reported insurance claims and recorded traffic accidents, examined across both temporal and spatial dimensions. Initially, the relationship between the number of issued insurance policies and the number of reported claims is formalized as an indicator of the correlation between the insurance coverage levels and exposure to risk. Subsequently, a trend analysis of damage frequency by age group is conducted for each year within the 2020–2024 period, with the aim of accurately identifying demographic differentiation of high-risk categories.

Within the annual regression analysis, third- and fourth-degree polynomial models are formulated to describe and predict the number and frequency of claims. These are supplemented by the implementation of a combined model that significantly enhances predictive accuracy. The spatial component of the analysis establishes a power-law dependence, modelling the relationship between the ranked territorial order of municipalities and the number of registered traffic incidents.

Model selection results from a systematic comparative evaluation based on criteria of statistical validity, analytical stability, and formal expressiveness, thereby enabling their application as effective instruments in risk management processes and decision-making within the field of road traffic safety.

Keywords: unregistered vehicles, traffic accidents, functional modelling, insurance claims, risk management

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern socioeconomic systems, mobility represents a critical element of sustainable development, with transportation playing a central role in ensuring the continuity and efficiency of the movement of people and goods. Traffic accidents, as an inevitable component of this process, entail substantial consequences not only in terms of human losses but also in respect to material damage and the resulting economic burden.

Insurance serves as the fundamental mechanism for compensating incurred damages, based on the principles of solidarity and risk distribution among all participants within the system. However, a particularly pressing issue arises in connection with traffic accidents caused by unregistered and uninsured vehicles, which create systemic gaps in insurance protection and compromise the right to compensation for affected parties.

In this context, the development of analytical and mathematical models for determining damages arising from such incidents becomes imperative. These models enable not only the identification of the scope and structure of risk but also the establishment of a foundation for planning compensatory mechanisms and preventive policies aimed at strengthening both the road traffic safety framework and the insurance protection system.

2. METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of this research is to develop an analytically valid model for determining the scope and structure of claims resulting from traffic accidents involving unregistered or uninsured vehicles. Motivated by the need to enhance institutional and financial mechanisms for compensating such claims, the study adopts an interdisciplinary approach that integrates elements of statistics, actuarial science, transport safety, and insurance regulation.

The methodological framework encompasses the processing and analysis of data obtained from relevant sources, including insurance companies, police traffic accident registries, and national motor vehicle databases. Through the application of regression analyses, correlation tests, and functional modeling techniques, quantitative relationships are established between the number of accidents, the share of unregistered vehicles, and the resulting claims. As noted by Evans (2004), statistical modeling of crash data enables the identification of underlying patterns that can be used to predict and prevent future accidents. In addition, risk assessment scenarios are developed, and the model's accuracy is validated through comparison with available empirical data.

Within the defined objective, the research comprises the following tasks:

- (1) identification and categorization of accidents involving unregistered vehicles;
- (2) determination of the frequency and types of claims associated with these events;
- (3) modeling of the functional dependence between unregulated factors and the extent of claim;
- (4) testing and verification of the model through the application of appropriate statistical indicators.

The implementation of this model aims to provide a deeper understanding of risk structures, enable the prediction of financial implications, and support the formulation of compensation and prevention policies for claims arising outside the standard insurance system.

3. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Within the scope of this research, a series of functional relationships were derived to model the behavior of claims associated with traffic accidents, with particular emphasis on cases involving unregistered vehicles. The results reveal a highly structured interconnection among key variables, enabling the formulation of models with strong predictive capability. As demonstrated by Haque, Chin, and Huang (2009), regression-based fault modeling improves the accuracy of predicting both the probability and severity of crash outcomes.

Initially, an analysis of data concerning the number of issued insurance policies and the number of reported claims established a clear positive functional dependence, reflecting the expected increase in claim-related occurrence as the base of the base of insured entities.

$$\text{Number of claims} = 0.0597 \cdot \text{number of policies} - 598.09$$

Figure 1. Relationship between the number of claims and the number of policies

Subsequently, an analysis of claim frequency by vehicle owner age groups during the 2020–2024 period revealed significant demographic distinctions. For each year, individual trend lines were derived as follows:

$$\text{Frequency} = \left(\frac{\text{claims}}{\text{policies}} \right) \cdot 100$$

Figure 2. Claim frequency by owner’s age (2020–2024)

Figure 3. Annual trends in policies, claims, and claim frequency

Within the annual regression analyses, the following dependencies were examined:

Dependency: Year → Number of claims

70% · Random Forest + 30% · Fourth – deg ree polinomial

Polinomial component

$$y = -5,264 \cdot 10^{12} + 7,808 \cdot 10^9 \cdot year - 3,860 \cdot 10^6 \cdot year^2 + 636,14 \cdot year^3$$

with a coefficient of determination of 0,898, MAE = 517,53 and RMSE = 565,76.

Dependency: Year → Accident frequency (%)

70% · Random Forest + 30% · Third – deg ree polinomial

Polinomial component

$$y = 91051930,24 - 0,5271 \cdot year - 133,774 \cdot year^2 + 0,08826 \cdot year^3 - 0,000016 \cdot year^4$$

with a coefficient of determination of 0,92084, MAE = 0,0563 and RMSE = 0,0607

Figure 4. Combined model of accident numbers and frequency (2020–2024)

In the spatial analysis section, the relationship between municipality (ordinal number) → number of recorded accidents is defined by the mathematical expression

$$y = 2522,43 \cdot x^{-0,6981}$$

where:

x = ordinal rank of the municipality (1 for Skopje, 2 for the municipality with the second highest number of accidents, etc.),

y = predicted number of accidents occurring within a given municipality, with a coefficient of determination of 0,92818, $MAE = 149,03$ and $RMSE = 152,52$

Figure 5. Power-law model of accidents number by municipality

Particular emphasis was placed on isolating and modeling claims caused by unregistered vehicles. Although such incidents are insufficiently documented in official databases, the application of indirect indicators and analytical scenarios enabled the development of models that reflect the probable severity and scope of these cases. As noted by Babić and Marić (2021), unregistered vehicles contribute significantly to the underreporting of traffic incidents and generate substantial discrepancies between recorded accidents and compensated claims.

The analytical approach, verified through statistical indicators of accuracy and relevance, confirms the applicability of the proposed models for institutional planning and financial forecasting purposes.

4. DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The obtained results confirm that traffic risk can be modeled with a high degree of precision through the appropriate selection of regression and combined analytical approaches. The consistency of the identified functional relationships, together with the high values of the coefficient of determination achieved by most models, indicates a well-structured connection between the independent and dependent variables across insurance datasets and traffic accident registries.

The polynomial models demonstrated a strong capacity to capture temporal trends in the data, particularly in the relationships between *year and number of claims*, as well as *year and claim frequency*. Mohan and Tiwari (2000) emphasized that effective road safety analysis in less-motorized environments requires the integration of empirical data with analytical modeling in order to capture the true dynamics of risk exposure. In this study, the implementation of a combined model that synthesizes the advantages of stochastic (machine based) and analytical approaches resulted in the lowest deviations and the highest predictive stability. This hybrid methodology illustrates the applicability of contemporary modeling techniques for improving accuracy when working with real-world, heterogeneous datasets.

The power-law dependence established between ranked municipalities and the number of recorded accidents provides a spatially balanced analytical framework and enables the identification of territorially concentrated risk zones. This finding serves as a

valuable basis for prioritizing preventive interventions and for directing institutional and financial resources toward the most vulnerable areas.

Particular importance is attributed to models addressing the issued of unregistered vehicles, a category that frequently remains outside the scope of formal insurance and compensation systems. The applied strategy of indirect identification and scenario-based simulation opens new perspectives for the quantitative documentation of risks that would otherwise remain insufficiently measurable. These findings have direct implications for the establishment of compensation funds, the adaptation of legislative frameworks, and the formulation of policies aimed at ensuring more equitable protection for affected parties.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research confirms that the application of appropriately selected functional models enables an in-depth and precise analysis of traffic risk, particularly in relation to accidents involving unregistered and uninsured vehicles. By integrating diverse data sources and applying polynomial, power-law, and combined regression models, the study identifies stable mathematical relationships that accurately reflect real-world conditions and trends within the domains of road traffic safety and insurance practice.

The high coefficient of determination, low deviations as measured by MAE and RMSE, and the robustness of the models – further validated through graphical and statistical analyses – affirm their relevance for practical implementation. Of particular significance are the models that provide a quantitative basis for estimating the potential burden imposed by unregistered vehicles within the traffic system, a category of risk that remains largely underexplored at both institutional and financial levels.

In light of these findings, the following measures are recommended:

- **Institutionalization of risk assessment models** that explicitly incorporate scenarios involving unregistered and uninsured vehicles, as an integral component of compensation fund planning and insurance reserve management.
- **Regulatory enhancement** aimed at formally incorporating these risks into national and regional insurance frameworks through the establishment of specialized protection schemes for affected parties.
- **Promotion of analytical modeling in practice** through strengthened cooperation among academic institutions, the insurance sector, and governmental bodies, with the objective of developing integrated systems for risk monitoring and management.
- **Continuous data collection and standardization**, as a prerequisite for ensuring the sustainability of the proposed models and their adaptability to evolving structural and technological conditions.

This research paves the way toward a more systematized approach to managing unfunded traffic risks and provides a solid foundation for further expansion of the modeling framework toward multivariate analysis and real-time predictive modeling.

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